

IMPACT OF FISCAL POLICY ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examines the Impact of Fiscal Policy on Economic Growth in Nigeria from 1980 to 2019. The specific objectives were to; test the causal relationship between fiscal policy and economic growth in Nigeria; empirically examine the impact of tax revenue on economic growth in Nigeria; empirically evaluate the impact of government recurrent expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria and to empirically investigate the impact of government capital expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria. Drawing extensively from the literature, two theories were used, namely; The Endogenous Growth Theory and The Keynesian Theory of Economic Growth. Time series data were used in the Study and Classical Ordinary Least Square (OLS) was the technique employed. The major findings from the study are out lined as follows: The estimated granger causality test shows evidence of no causality or independence between fiscal policy and economic growth in Nigeria; Tax revenue recorded a negative though statistically insignificant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria; Government recurrent expenditure showed a positive but statistically insignificant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria. Government capital expenditure disclosed an insignificant negative relationship with economic growth in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that government should close all loopholes (leakages) in tax collection to ensure that tax proceeds are remitted in full to respective tax authorities, government should make concerted effort to channel tax proceeds to development oriented projects so that both short and long term gains would be realized.

Keywords: Fiscal Policy, Economic Growth, Government Capital Expenditure, Government Recurrent Revenue, Endogeneous Growth Theory.

1. Introduction

In the past decades, the Nigerian economy had been weighed down by several challenges. AL-Yousif and Abdullah (2000), Ranjan and Sharma (2008) and Cooray (2009) had identified some of these challenges as; gross mismanagement/misappropriation of public funds, corruption and ineffective economic policies, lack of integration of macroeconomic plans and the absence of harmonization and coordination of fiscal policies as well as inappropriate and ineffective economic stabilization policies.

Amadi (2006) noted that reckless government spending and weak sectorial linkages and other socioeconomic maladies constitute the bane of rapid economic growth and development in Nigerian. Hence, fiscal policy is an important economic tool used by the government to distribute and redistribute income and welfare. “Undoubtedly, fiscal policy is central to the health of any economy, as government’s power to tax and to spend affects the disposable income of citizens and corporations, as well as the general business climate”. (Abata, Kehinde and Bolarinwa, 2012).

According to Okafor (2012), in Nigeria, public spending takes the form of capital expenditure and recurrent expenditure; capital spending includes expenditure on public works and goods, while recurrent spending includes expenditure used for maintaining the work force (salaries and allowances). The basic Keynesian analysis showed that increasing public spending induces investment, income, economic growth and consequently improves economic well-being.

In a bid to use fiscal policy to achieve economic growth and welfare in Nigeria, Federal Government adopted a medium term fiscal policy framework (MTEF) whose theme was fiscal consolidation, job creation and inclusive growth. This had also widened the revenue generation through more efficient tax reforms and boosting the non-oil sector. For instance, 2012 federal budget theme was “fiscal consolidation and job creation”. In that respect, government effort was to invest in key priority sectors such as; power, agriculture, education, housing, transport (railways), direct job creation, roads and rail projects, maternal and child health programs, subsidy reinvestment programme and aviation. In their efforts to reduce the cost of governance, the federal government resolved to rationalize government agencies with overlapping functions. This led to some modest savings that would be invested back into productive sectors towards achieving the desired level of economic growth in Nigeria (Federal Ministry of Finance, 2012). Further, the federal government in a bid to fight corruption in the country, a treasury single account was introduced to consolidate all inflows from all agencies of government into a single account at the central bank in order to enthrone centralised; transparent and accountable revenue management; facilitate effective cash management; ensure cash availability and promote financial efficiency.

Fiscal policy is a major economic stabilization weapon that involves measures taken to regulate and control the volume, cost and availability, as well as direction of money in an economy to achieve some macroeconomic objectives and counteract undesirable trends in the economy (Gbosi, 1998). It is also a tool of macroeconomic management used by the government to regulate the economy via its revenue and expenditure portfolios. The revenue portfolio consists of components like tax revenue, trade surplus, and foreign aid, while the expenditure portfolio consists of recurrent and capital expenditure. In other words, fiscal policy is government's conscious actions towards spending money and for levying taxes aimed at influencing macro-economic variables so as to achieve desired macroeconomic objectives. The relationship between fiscal policy and economic growth has been discussed extensively in the literature using empirical analysis. According to Tanzi and Zee (1997) there are three cardinal indicators of fiscal policy – government expenditure, taxes, and deficit financing.

The importance of fiscal policy emanates from the fact that public spending is considered the prime driver of economic activities in a country because it influences the level of aggregate demand which invariably promotes economic growth. Public revenues serve as the main sources of income for a country while public debt is part of the government's spending, whether internal or external. Because of this, this paper attempts to empirically investigate the causal relationship between fiscal policy and economic growth as well as evaluating the impact of fiscal policy on economic growth in Nigeria. Sequel to the dwindling economic growth recorded in the past years resulting in the country experiencing economic recession recently, there was complete loss of confidence in the economy. A lot of local and foreign companies were closing their shops as they could no longer cope with the rising production cost.

The cyclical fluctuations in Nigeria's economic activities often caused the periodical rise in the country's capital expenditure, low recurrent expenditure, high government taxes, rising unemployment, progressive rise in inflation rates and decline in economic growth (Ndiyo and Udah 2003). However, the Nigerian economy started experiencing recession from early 1980s that caused depression in the mid-1980s. The depression continued until early 1990s without recovering from it (CBN 2016). As such, the government continually initiated policy measures that would tackle and overcome the dwindling economy. Drawing from the experience of the great depression, government policy measures to curb the depressed economy was in the form of increase in government expenditure or spending both capital and recurrent and also reduction in her taxes to achieve the desired level of economic growth (Nagayasu 2003). In spite of increase in government expenditure and reduction in taxes, the Nigerian economy is yet to record the desired level of economic growth (CBN 2012).

According to Okunronmu (1993), the management of the Nation's economy to achieve macroeconomic stability had been unproductive and indeed negative. This is evidence in the adverse inflationary trend, government fiscal deficit, the undulating foreign exchange rates, the fall and rise of gross domestic product, unfavourable balance of payment as well as increasing unemployment rates are all symptoms of growing macroeconomic instability (Onoh 2007).

The budgeted amount for spending in annual budgets in Nigeria had never declined over the years, evidence reveals that there was a substantial increase in government spending, primary deficit, and debt in Nigeria between 1991 and 2005 (CBN Statistical Bulletin, 2012).

However, issues of hunger, poor infrastructural development, inequality, high mortality rate, poverty, etc. pervade the Nigerian society. This is one area that is a cause of concern for policy makers. There have been macroeconomic imbalances of varying degrees in Nigeria, such as inappropriate public expenditure and revenue policies, large deficit in the public sector have been identified by experts as responsible for the macroeconomic disequilibrium (Ajisafe and Folorunso, 2002).

In Nigeria, the nexus between fiscal policy and economic growth is not well defined. The current practical experience which is a departure from theoretical giving brings up reason for a detailed empirical study to attempt to uncover reasons for observed departure from theory.

This paper is structured as follows; section 2 covers the literature review of the major works in the field, section 3 presents methodology. Section 4 discusses the results and section 5 concludes the paper.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Theoretical Framework

This section tries to address the diverging theories of economics that have established link between fiscal policy and economic growth. It provides an overview of various theoretical predictions to facilitate interpretation of the empirical findings undertaken under fiscal policy implementation and economic growth.

2.1.1 The Endogenous Growth Theory

The theoretical underpinning for this study is basically the endogenous growth theory which advocates the stimulation of level and growth rate of per capita output through within the model using fiscal policy (e.g., government spending).

The traditional neoclassical growth model assumes that output is a function of capital and labor, while technology is given:

$$Y = Af(K, L)$$

Where Y output, A is technology, being exogenous, while capital (K) and labour (L) are endogenous factors.

In the New Growth Model (Endogenous Growth Model), technology is viewed as endogenously determined:

$$Y = f(K, L, A).$$

Technology (A) refers to rate of investment, (K) is the investment in capital stock and (L) is the human capital.

This model emphasizes greater role of government in improving the efficiency or resource allocation and promoting investment to raise the rate of economic growth in the developing countries (Ahuja, 2009). The government can directly make adequate investment in economic infrastructure such as power, communication, roads, and highways and in human capital, which promotes private investment and generate increasing returns to scale. Though, in many aspects, endogenous growth theory is a mere extension of the neoclassical theory of growth. It, however, makes a departure from the neoclassical policy of free market and passive role of government. More specifically, models of the growth effects of fiscal policy are usually built on the basis of Barro and Sala-Martin (1992) framework. This study draws inspiration from these studies by employing a production function in which government expenditure and taxation enter as inputs. The choice of this framework is owed to its simplicity in application and availability of time series data in Nigeria.

2.1.2 The Keynesian Theory of Economic Growth

The Keynesians are the twentieth century economists who embraced and also broadened John Maynard Keynes's principle in the existence of incessant unemployment equilibrium, dissimilar to the classical economists' idea on Say's law of market arguing that market economy are self-adjusting therefore there is no need for the government involvement in the economy. They believe that fiscal policy and not monetary policy is the most powerful policy measures to make the economy stable and move it forward. They are sometimes referred to as Demand-side economists. Keynes accepts that the forces of demand and supply could not attain full employment condition. Keynesians therefore insisted that only government interference (public sector) through the use of unrestricted policy measures would take the free enterprise economy out of depression and ensure steady growth. Variations in savings and investments are responsible for modifications in business activities and employment in an economy.

The role of fiscal policy in the achievement of macroeconomic objectives has been extensively dealt with the Keynesian Theory of an activist macroeconomic policy. The Keynesian analysis leads to the conclusion that demand management policies can and should be used to improve macroeconomic performance. An activist macroeconomic policy involves setting monetary and fiscal variables in each time period at the values which are thought necessary to achieve the government's objectives. A basic premise of Keynesian economics is that the private sector is inherently unstable. It is subject to frequent and quantitatively important disturbances in the components of aggregate demand.

The broad objectives of Keynesian macroeconomic policy are not in dispute, these objectives are full employment, a stable price level, the absence of significant deviations of output from its equilibrium time path, a satisfactory rate of economic growth, an equitable distribution of income, and balance of payment equilibrium. There exist, however, differing opinions, regarding the priorities accorded to these objectives. Keynesian activist policy has come under increasing attack from the monetarist and classical schools, which regard the private sector as inherently stable. They do not deny that random disturbances occur in the private sector but they do not think that these are either large or further amplified by quantifying adjustments. The private sector adjusts via relative price changes to such disturbance quite adequately, so active stabilization policy is not required. Furthermore, it (stabilization policy) may, if implemented increase rather than diminish fluctuations in output and employment. Nevertheless, stabilization policy requires that policy makers can determine feasible and can effectively control the instrumental variables.

Keynesian theory posits that removing spending from the economy will reduce level of aggregate demand and stabilizing prices. However, recent researchers have made an impact to the development of fiscal policy and economic growth through their contribution to the theoretical issues on this study.

2.2 Empirical Literature

Many studies on the relationship between fiscal policy and growth were conducted before the relevant endogenous growth models were developed. Landau (1983) using cross-sectional data from 104 countries found a negative relation between public consumption as share of GDP and growth per capita using Summers-Heston data, while Koremendi-meguire (1985) using cross-section/time series data for 57 countries found no statistically significant relation of the same variables for the post-world War II period. Koester and Kormendi (1989) reported that marginal tax rates have a significant negative relationship with the level of per capita GDP only and not with economic growth. Factors that influence the effect of government size on economic growth many studies have stressed the role of a number of factors that can

influence the magnitude and significance of the effect of government size on economic growth.

Barro (1989), with data from 98 countries in the post-World War II period, found that government consumption decrease per capita growth, while public investment does not affect growth. Levine-Renelt (1992) found that most results from earlier studies on the relationship between long-run growth and fiscal policy indicators are fragile to small changes in the conditioning set.

Also, the dynamic effects of fiscal policy are either ignored completely or not modeled carefully in existing empirical work. Moreover, even if there is correlation between explanatory variables and the rate of growth, the direction of causation is not clear (Wagner's law). Besides these, there might be correlation of fiscal variables with initial GDP (Easterly-Rebello, 1993).

Cashin (1995) estimated a positive relationship between government transfers, public investment and growth and a negative one between distortionary taxes and growth from panel data for 23 developed countries between 1971 and 1988. Devarajan *et al.* (1996) showed that public current expenditures increase growth, whilst government capital spending decreases growth in 43 developing countries over 1970–1990

The potential impacts of fiscal policy on long-term growth have also generated substantial debate (Tanzi and Zee, 1996). Endogenous growth models suggest that fiscal policy can either promote or retard growth as investment in human and physical capital, which can be affected by taxation and government expenditures, can impact on steady-state growth rates (Barro, 1991; Chamlay, 1986; King and Rebelo, 1990; Jone *et al* 1993; Barro and Sala-i-Martin, 1995; Mendoza *et al.* 1997).

Philips (1997) critically analyzed the Nigerian fiscal policy between 1960 and 1997 with a view to suggesting workable ways for the effective implementation of vision 2010. He observed that budget deficits have been an abiding feature in Nigeria for decades. He noted that except for the period 1971 to 1974, and 1979, there has been an overall deficit in the Federal Government budgets each year since 1960 to date. The chronic budget deficits and their financing largely by borrowing, he asserted, have resulted in excessive money supply, worsened inflationary pressures, and complicated macroeconomic instability, resulting in negative impact on external balance, investment, employment and growth. He, however, contended that fiscal policy will be an effective tool for moving Nigeria towards the desired state in 2010 only if it is substantially cured of the chronic budget deficit syndrome it has suffered for decades.

A countless of studies have examined the relationship between fiscal policy and growth in developed, developing and emerging economies of the world. However, one of the pioneer studies of fiscal policy and growth can be traced to the work of Kneller et al; (1999) argued that the biases related to the incomplete specification of the government budget constraint present in previous studies are significant and after taking them into account, they found for a panel of 22 OECD countries for 1970 - 1995 that distortionary taxation hampers growth, while non-distortionary taxes do not; the study further revealed that productive government expenditure increases growth, while non-productive expenditure does not.

Poot (2000) in a survey of published articles in 1983 – 1998 did not find conclusive evidence for the relationship between government consumption and growth, while he found empirical support for the negative effect of taxes on growth. Also, he reported a positive link between growth and education spending, while the evidence on the negative growth impact of defense spending is moderately strong.

Adenikinju and Olofin (2000) focused on the role of economic policy in the growth performance of the manufacturing sectors in African countries. They utilized panel data for seventeen African countries over the period of 1976 to 1993. Their econometric evidence indicates that government policies aimed at encouraging foreign direct investment, enhancing the external competitiveness of the economy, and maintaining macroeconomic growth performance in Africa.

Easterly (2005) discovered a significant growth effect of budget balance, which disappeared when extreme observations were excluded from the analysis. It implies therefore that there is widespread non-robustness of coefficient signs and statistical significance even within similar specifications for similar variables. There are some possible explanations for these differences. The most important, in our opinion, is the absence of a generally accepted theoretical framework to guide the empirical research (Galor, 2005).

Amanja and Morrissey (2005) contributed to a theoretical and empirical debate on the question whether or not fiscal policy stimulates growth in the long run. They believed that government's involvement in economic activity is vital for growth, but an opposing view holds that government operations are inherently bureaucratic and inefficient and, therefore, stifles rather than promotes growth. They used time series annual data to investigate the relationship of various measures of fiscal policy on growth. Categorizing government expenditure into productive and unproductive and tax revenue into distortionary and non-distortionary, the study found out that unproductive expenditure and non-distortionary tax revenue do not contribute to growth as predicted by economic theory.

In the same vein, Olawunmi and Ayinka (2007) examined the contribution of fiscal policy in the achievement of sustainable economic growth in Nigeria using Solow growth model estimated with the use of ordinary least square method. It was found that fiscal policy has not been effective in the area of promoting sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. They however, stated that factors such as wasteful spending, poor policy implementation and lack of feedback mechanism for implemented policy evident in Nigeria which are indeed capable of hampering the effectiveness of fiscal policy have made it impossible to come up with such a conclusion.

Adefeso and Mobalaji (2010) examined on the fiscal-monetary policy and economic growth in Nigeria. Their major objective was to re-estimate and re-examine the relative effectiveness of fiscal and monetary policies on economic growth in Nigeria using annual data from 1970 – 2007. The Error correction mechanism and co-integration technique were employed to analyze the data and draw policy inferences. Their result showed that the effect of monetary policy is much stronger than fiscal policy. They suggested that there should be more emphasis and reliance on monetary policy for the purpose of economic stabilization in Nigeria.

A study by Abu *et al*; (2010) uses co-integration and error correction methods to analyze the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth. This study, which is based on the Keynesian and Endogenous growth models, revealed that government total capital expenditure, total recurrent expenditure and growth expenditure on education have negative effect on economic growth. He also maintained that, on the contrary, rising government expenditure on transport and communication and health results to an increase in economic growth.

Victor (2011) investigated economic, political and institutional constraints to fiscal policy implementation in sub-Saharan Africa. It was found that planned fiscal adjustments or expansions are less likely to be implemented. The larger they are, the more inaccurate the growth forecasts they are based on. The finding supports ongoing efforts in the region to improve quality and timeliness of economic data, enhance forecasting capacity, adopt realistic fiscal plans, and strength governance, budgetary institutions, and public financial management procedures.

Ogbole, Amadi and Essi (2011) conducted a work on fiscal policy; its impact on economic growth in Nigeria (1970 – 2006). The study involves comparative analysis of the impact of fiscal policy on economic growth in Nigeria during regulation and deregulation periods. Econometric analysis of time series data from Central Bank of Nigeria was conducted. Results showed that there is difference in the effectiveness of fiscal policy in stimulating economic growth during and after regulation period.

Appropriate policy mix, prudent public spending, setting of achievable fiscal policy targets and diversification of the nation's economic base, among others, were recommended.

Peter and Simeon (2011) investigated the impact of fiscal policy variables on Nigeria's economic growth between 1970 and 2009. The study employed Vector Auto Regression (VAR) and error correction mechanism techniques. The study revealed that there exist a long-run equilibrium relationship between economic growth and fiscal policy variables in Nigeria. Consequently, it was recommended that government should formulate and implement viable fiscal policy options that will stabilize the economy. This could be achieved through the practice of true fiscal federalism and the decentralization of the various levels of government in Nigeria.

Olasunkanmi and Babatunde (2012) investigated the fiscal policy variables that contributed to growth in Nigeria between 1981 and 2010 in a view to hypothesize the fiscal policy variables-growth effect. The variables utilized were productive expenditure, unproductive expenditure, distortionary taxes, non-distortionary taxes, fiscal deficit and real growth rate of GDP. The results of fiscal-growth effect model discovered that productive expenditure, distortionary taxes and fiscal deficit contribute to growth in Nigeria. Furthermore, non-distortionary tax was found to exert significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

Audu (2012) evaluated the causal relationship between money supply, fiscal deficits and exports as means of analyzing the impact of fiscal policy on the growth of the Nigerian economy between 1970 and 2010. The study employed the Error Correction Model and two band recursive least square to test for the stability of variables on economic growth. The findings showed a significant causal relationship between GDP, fiscal deficit, money supply and export. The study maintained that fiscal policies have significant influence on output growth of the Nigerian economy.

In Oseni and Onakoya (2012), the researchers aimed at testing the argument that only three fiscal variables (productive expenditure, distortionary tax and fiscal deficit) contribute to growth by using annual time-series data of Nigeria from 1981 to 2010. The study found that in the case of Nigeria, four fiscal variables (productive government expenditure, unproductive government expenditure, distortionary taxes, non-distortionary taxes, government budget deficit) contribute immensely to growth either positively or negatively. Chude and Chude (2013) studied the impact of government expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria. This study investigates the effects of public expenditure in education on economic growth in Nigeria over a period from 1977 to 2012, using co-integration error correction model (ECM). The result indicated that total expenditure on education is highly and statistically

significant and has positive relationship with economic growth in Nigeria in the long run. The researchers concluded that economic growth is clearly impacted by factors both exogenous and endogenous to the public expenditure in Nigeria.

Agu, Idike and Okwor (2014) appraised the impact of various components of fiscal policy on the Nigerian economy between 1961 and 2010. The study disaggregated fiscal policy into government spending on administration, social and community services and economic services. The results showed that total government expenditures have tended to increase with government revenues. Investment expenditure was found to be much lower than recurrent expenditures evidencing poor growth in the country's economy. In addition, the results showed that government expenditure on economic services is positively related to economic growth. An increase in budgetary allocation to economic services will lead to enhancement in economic stability.

Babalola and Aminu (2014) examined the impact of fiscal policy in Nigeria between 1977 and 2009. Fiscal policy was captured by government productive expenditure, unproductive expenditure, distortionary and non-distortionary taxation. The study employed the Augmented-Dickey Fuller test, Co-integration test and Error Correction Model. The findings revolved that productive government expenditure has long-run positive impact on economic growth. Unexpectedly, distortionary taxation positively impacted economic growth. The study maintained that government should increase its spending on health, education and economic service, as components of productive expenditure to boost economic growth. Onwe (2014) examined the impacts of fiscal policy components on economic growth in Nigeria between 1980 and 2012. Expenditure on administration, economic services, social and community services, transfers and ratio of federal government expenditure to GDP are regressed on GDP growth rate. The results of the regression analysis revealed that expenditure on administration, social and community services and ratio of federal government expenditure to GDP have positive impact on economic growth while expenditure on transfers and economic services has negative impact on economic growth in Nigeria. The study maintained that fiscal policy components have no robust impact on economic growth in Nigeria within the estimated period.

Osuala and Jones (2014) employed the autoregressive distributed lag model to empirically analyze the impact of fiscal policy on economic growth in Nigeria between 1986 and 2010. The fiscal policy variables considered in the study include government recurrent and capital expenditure, non-oil taxes and government debt. The findings revealed an evidence of long run equilibrium relationship between fiscal policy and economic growth within the period estimated. Government recurrent and capital expenditure were found to have significant and positive impact

on economic growth while non-oil taxes and government debts have no significant impact on real GDP. Only capital expenditure had short-run equilibrium relationship with economic growth. Ugwanta (2014) determined the effect of fiscal policy variables on economic growth of selected Sub-Saharan African countries. Government productive and unproductive expenditure and distortionary and non-distortionary taxes are used to measure fiscal policy. The results of the panel least square showed that government productive and unproductive expenditure as well as distortionary. The results showed that budget balances of some selected nation have positive correlation with economic growth. Falade and Folorunsho (2015) examined the relative effectiveness of fiscal and monetary policy instruments on economic growth in Nigeria in order to determine the appropriate mix of both policies. The study employed the error correction mechanism between 1970 and 2013. Real GDP was expressed as a function of money supply, exchange rate, interest rate (monetary policy instruments), government revenue, government expenditure (fiscal policy instruments) gross capital formation and inflation rate (control variables). The results showed that all the fiscal and monetary policy variables attained stationary. The results also showed a long-run relationship among fiscal and monetary variables and economic growth. The study maintained that the current level of exchange rate and its previous level, interest rate and current level of government expenditure and money supply are the suitable appropriate policy mix in promoting economic growth in Nigeria in short-run and long-run.

Halkos and Paizanos (2015) used cross-section data for 100 countries for 1970 – 1988 and panel data for 28 countries for 1870 – 1988. They found that public transportation, communication and educational investment are positively correlated with growth per capital and aggregate public investment is negatively correlated with growth per capital, although they admitted that many fiscal policy variables are highly correlated with initial income levels and fiscal variables are potentially endogenous.

Abdulrauf (2015) examined the short and long run impact of fiscal policy on economic development in Nigeria between 1981 and 2013. The study used government recurrent expenditure, government capital expenditure, government investment and tax revenue to indicate fiscal policy. Economic development was poised by real per capital income. The study employed the vector error correction model. The results revealed that government recurrent expenditure and government investment have significant positive impact on economic development in both the short and long run. Capital expenditure appeared to have a short run positive impact but not in the long run. Tax revenue has negative significant impact in both short and long run. The speed of adjustment to long run equilibrium stood at 115%. In addition, existing empirical studies on fiscal policy and growth differ in terms of

countries included in the sample, period/method of estimation and measures of public sector activity. Data quality is also a problem since, various countries have different conventions for the measurement of public sector size and there are limited data at the required level of disaggregation, implying measurement errors. Furthermore, the linear structure imposed on most empirical models is convenient but not necessarily realistic and consistent with the underlying theory (Halkos and Paizanos 2015).

Maku (2015) examined the impact of fiscal policy on economic growth in Nigeria between 1970 and 2011. The study employed the Engle-Granger co-integration for long-run relationship, ordinary least square for long run estimate and diagnostic test for consistency of instruments. Economic growth was measured by real gross domestic product while fiscal balance was used to denote fiscal policy. Macroeconomic indices such as gross capital formation, broad money supply and exchange rate were captured in the study. The results revealed fiscal policy exerted significant positive effect on economic growth, which indicates that appropriate fiscal measures stimulate economic growth in Nigeria. The study maintained that government spending has greater impact on the growth rate of the Nigerian economy.

Oshinowo (2015) broadly examined the effect of fiscal policy on sectorial output growth in Nigeria between 1970 and 2013. The study employed autoregressive distributed lag model and error correction model. The study investigated the effect of total fiscal expenditure on growth on agriculture, manufacturing, building and construction, mining and services sectors. The result showed that total fiscal expenditure has positively contributed to all the sectors' output except the agriculture. The study maintained dichotomy between sectoral responses to fiscal policy variables.

Tchokote and Ibe (2016) studied the consequence of monetary and fiscal policies on economic growth in Nigeria. The study adopted correlation analysis, unit-root, ordinary least square and granger causality test on selected fiscal and monetary policies variables – money supply, interest rate, and government revenue and expenditure. The results showed that money supply exerts greater impact on growth than government expenditure.

Abubakar (2016) investigated the impact of fiscal policy shocks on growth and unemployment in Nigeria between 1981 and 2015. The study employed the structural vector autoregressive methodology coupled with unit and co-integration tests. The results showed that shock in public expenditure have positive long-lasting effect on output while revenue shock was found to exert a positive effect (lower than that of public expenditure shock) on output. However, the effect of revenue shock on

unemployment was found to be negative but short-lived. Odetayo and Adeyemi (2017) examined fiscal policy sustainability and economic growth in Nigeria between 1980 and 2015. The study adopted the error correction model and autoregressive distributed lag model to analyze the effect on government spending and fiscal deficit grew massively within the period considered. The results equally revealed that fiscal policy is weakly sustainable in Nigeria.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1.1 Research Design

The research design adopted in this work is causal experimental research; this method is adjudged appropriate because it attempt to establish a cause and effect relationship among the variables of interest in the study.

3.2 Model Specifications

The main task in this sub-section is to attempt to model the relationship between fiscal policy and economic growth in Nigeria. Drawing extensively from theoretical framework and empirical literature, we therefore, make an effort to model the measure of economic growth on a vector of relevant explanatory variable.

3.2.2. Model 1: The Causal Relationship between Fiscal Policy and Economic Growth in Nigeria

This model specifies the causal direction between fiscal policy and economic growth. In other words, the model is to determine the directional causality between fiscal policy and economic growth in Nigeria. Causality is assumed when lagged values of a variable X_i have explanatory power in a regression of a variable Y_i that contains lagged values of Y_i and X_i . Therefore, following the standard Pair-Wise Granger causality to test the direction of causality between fiscal policy and economic growth taking cognizance of their integrations, we specify the Granger causality in the equations below:

$$\Delta GDP_{gt} = \sum_{i=l}^m \alpha_i \Delta TR_{t-i} + \sum_{j=l}^m \beta_j \Delta GDP_{gt-j} + \mu_{1t} \quad (3.1a)$$

$$\Delta TR_t = \sum_{i=l}^m \pi_i \Delta GDP_{gt-i} + \sum_{j=l}^m \delta_j \Delta TR_{t-j} + \mu_{2t} \quad (3.1b)$$

$$\Delta GDP_{gt} = \sum_{i=l}^m \alpha_i \Delta GRE_{t-i} + \sum_{j=l}^m \beta_j \Delta GDP_{gt-j} + e_{1t} \quad (3.1c)$$

$$\Delta GRE_t = \sum_{i=l}^m \pi_i \Delta GDP_{gt-i} + \sum_{j=l}^m \delta_j \Delta GRE_{t-j} + e_{2t} \quad (3.1d)$$

$$\Delta \text{GDPg}_t = \sum_{i=l}^m \alpha_i \Delta \text{GCE}_{t-i} + \sum_{j=l}^m \beta_j \Delta \text{GDPg}_{t-j} + \epsilon_{1t} \quad (3.1e)$$

$$\Delta \text{GCE}_t = \sum_{i=l}^m \pi_i \Delta \text{GDPg}_{t-i} + \sum_{j=l}^m \delta_j \Delta \text{GCE}_{t-j} + \epsilon_{2t} \quad (3.1f)$$

Where:

= the first difference operator

β, π , are coefficients

i and j = lagged period

t = time

$\mu_{1t}, \mu_{2t}, \epsilon_{1t}, \epsilon_{2t}$, and ϵ_{it} = uncorrelated whitenoise

m = maximum number of lags

GDPg = Gross domestic product growth rate

TR = Tax revenue

GRE = Government recurrent expenditure

GCE = Government Capital expenditure

3.2.2 Model 2: The Impact of Tax Revenue on Economic Growth

The Neoclassical model of economic growth is adopted as the analytical framework for this study. This model emphasizes capital, labour and technological progress as the determinants of economic growth. The focus is restricted to technological progress in the form of fiscal policy indicators. The relationship between economic growth and the variables is expressed in the form of a production function below.

$$Y = f(K, L, T) \quad (3.2)$$

Where Y = gross domestic product (GDP)

K = Stock of capital

L = Labour force

T = Technological progress

The relationship between growth and fiscal policy measured by tax revenue can be specified as:

$$\text{GDPg}_t = f(\text{INV}_t, \text{LFPR}_t, \text{TR}_t, \text{INF}_t, \text{EXR}_t) \quad (3.3)$$

Where GDPg = gross domestic product growth rate

INV = Investment (gross fixed capital formation)

LFPR = Labour force participators rate

TR = Tax revenue

EXR = exchange rate

Equation 3.3 could be stated in an econometric form as:

$$\text{GDPg}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{INV}_t + \beta_2 \text{LFPR}_t + \beta_3 \text{TR}_t + \beta_4 \text{IBF}_t + \beta_5 \text{EXR}_t + U_t \quad (3.4)$$

Where β_0 = constant term

$\beta_0 - \beta_0 =$ slope parameters
 $ut =$ disturbance term
 $\beta_1 > 0, \beta_2 > 0, \beta_3 > 0, \beta_4 < 0, \beta_5 < 0.$

3.2.3 Model 3: The impact of Government Recurrent Expenditure on Growth

The relationship between fiscal policy measured by government recurrent expenditure can be expressed as:

$$GDPg = f(INV_t, LFPR_t, Ms_t, GRE_t, OPN_t) \quad (3.5)$$

Where $GDPg =$, $INV =$, $LFPR =$ Labour force participation rate, $Ms =$ money supply, $ERE =$, $OPN =$ Trade Openness

Equation 3.5 could be stated in an econometric form as:

$$GDPg_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 INV_t + \alpha_2 LFPR_t + \alpha_3 Ms_t + \alpha_4 GRE_t + \alpha_5 OPN_t + e_t \quad (3.6)$$

Where $\alpha_0 =$ constant term

$\alpha_1 - \alpha_5 =$ slope parameters

$e_t =$ disturbance term

$\alpha_1 > 0, \alpha_2 > 0, \alpha_3 > 0, \alpha_4 > 0, \alpha_5 > 0$

3.2.4 Model 4: The Impact of Government Capital Expenditure on Growth

The relationship between fiscal policy measured by government capital expenditure can be expressed as:

$$GDPg_t = f(INV_t, LFg_t, GCE_t, INF_t, Ca_t) \quad (3.7)$$

Where $GDPg$, INV , $LFg =$ Labour force growth rate, GCE , INF , $CA =$ Current account as a ratio of GDP

Equation 3.7 could be stated in an econometric form as:

$$GDPg_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 INV_t + \alpha_2 LFg_t + \alpha_3 GCE_t + \alpha_4 INF_t + \alpha_5 Ca_t + e_t \quad (3.8)$$

Where $\alpha_0 =$ Constant term

$\alpha_1 - \alpha_5 =$ slope parameters

$e_t =$ error term

$\alpha_1 > 0, \alpha_2 > 0, \alpha_3 > 0, \alpha_4 < 0, \alpha_5 > 0$

1.1 Estimation Technique

This work uses Ordinary Least Square (OLS). We will also conduct a Granger Causality test to trace the direction of causality between fiscal policy and economic growth. However, since the variables in the models are time series, there is likelihood that unit root is associated with them or that the series are non-stationary or exhibit random walk. Therefore, there is need to determine their properties with respect to mean reverting or stochastic time variant mean tendencies.

3.3.1 Granger Causality

The Granger (1969) approach to the question of whether X Granger causes Y is to see then how much of the current y can be explained by past values of y and then to see whether adding lagged values of X can improve the explanation. Y is said to be Granger caused by X if X helps in the prediction of y or equivalently if the coefficients on the lagged X's are statistically significant.

Note also that, Granger causality is more of an indicator of precedence than a real causal identification (Geda, Ndungu and Zerfu 2012). Majority of time series studies have used the Granger causality test to examine the causality between macroeconomic variables.

3.3.2 Unit Root Tests

Time series data tend to exhibit either a deterministic or stochastic trend and are therefore non-stationary. Prior to testing for the direction of causality between the time series, the first step is to check stationary of the variable used in the models. The aim of this test is to establish whether the time series have a stationary trend, and, if non-stationary, to show the order of integration when non-stationary time series data are used in a regression model, the result may spuriously indicate significant relationship when they actually do not exist.

3.4 Sources of Data

Secondary data were used for the study. The data were drawn from the publication of the Central Bank of Nigeria, National Bureau of Statistics and World Development Indicator. The data set consists of annual time series for Nigeria from 1980 – 2019.

2. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Following the fact that our data are time series, we followed the standard practice in econometrics by first conducting preliminary diagnostics test on the time series properties of all the variables included in the model before estimation.

4.1 Unit Root Tests

Table 4.1 Augmented Dickey Fuller Statistic

Variable	first Difference	Integration
Model		
GDPg	-8.9343 (-4.23)	I(1)
GCE	-5.3633(-4.23)	I(1)
EXR	-4.6129(-4.23)	I(1)
CA	-5.9964(-4.23)	I(1)
GRE	-7.6492(-4.23)	I(1)
INF	-5.6963(-4.23)	I(1)
LFGR	-6.5954(-4.23)	I(1)
INV	-4.4357(-4.23)	I(1)
LPR	-10.4220(-4.23)	I(1)
M2	-6.4468(-4.23)	I(1)
OPN	-7.9584(-4.23)	I(1)
TXR	-8.3683(-4.23)	I(1)

Source: Author's compilation using E-views 7

Note: Numbers in brackets represent critical values at 1% probability level variables are as defined in chapter 3.

In order to check the time series properties of the variables used in the model, the above table shows the result of the unit root test, which showed that all the variables were integrated of order one I(1) at 1% significant level. However, the result shows no influence of structural break in the model.

4.2 Granger Causality Test Result

It is necessary to know the direction of causality between fiscal policy and economic growth in Nigeria. The Granger causality test result shed light on this by using the lag specification as obtained from E-views.

Table 4.2: Pair-wise Granger Causality Tests

Null hypothesis	Obs.	f-statistic	Prob.	Decision	Direction
Tax revenue does not Granger cause GDPG	36	1.26062	0.2976	Accept	No causality
GDPG does not Granger cause tax revenue	36	1.33451	0.2780	Accept	No causality
GRE does not Granger cause GDPG	36	0.56017	0.5768	Accept	No causality
GDPG does not Granger cause GRE	36	2.73120	0.0808	Accept	No causality
GCE does not Granger cause GDPG	36	0.42310	0.6581	Accept	No causality
GDPG does not Granger cause GCE	36	0.23762	0.7899	Accept	No causality

Source: computed by the author using E-views

From Table 4.2 above, the result shows that all null hypotheses are accepted which implies an insignificant p-value for all the variables. By implication, it reveals the case of independence, meaning that the set of fiscal policy measured by tax revenue, Government recurrent expenditure and government capital expenditure as well as gross domestic product growth rate are not statistically significant at 1%, 5% and 10% in the regressions.

4.2.1 Test of Hypothesis ($H_0:1$)

The hypothesis that there is no causal relationship between fiscal policy and economic growth in Nigeria is answered based on the result obtained in Table 4.2. Using the F-statistic result for all variables and comparing it with the critical value, and checking their individual p-values, the null hypothesis is accepted. By this, the decision rule follows that we do not reject the null hypothesis if f-statistic is less than the critical value.

Therefore, since the F-statistic values are all less than the critical values, we do not reject the null hypothesis which concludes that there is no causal relationship between fiscal policy and economic growth in Nigeria. The findings were at variance with the works of Audu (2012) and Amanja and Morrissey (2005).

Table 4.3: Relationship between Fiscal Policy and Economic Growth in Nigeria

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-statistic
	Prob.		
C	1.894774	19.58860	0.096728
	0.9236		
INV	-0.228544	0.240089	-0.951916
	0.3493		
TXR	-0.160571	0.364032	-0.441090
	0.6625		
INF	0.184929	0.238232	0.778252
	0.4441		
EXR	0.015988	0.028034	0.570301
	0.5730		
M ₂	0.099890	0.538592	0.185465
	0.8542		
GRE	48.47851	93.26125	0.519814
	0.6073		
OPN	0.020881	0.115082	0.181445
	0.8573		
GCE	-4.638006	5.291510	-0.876500
	0.3882		
CA	0.197251	0.381409	0.517163
	0.6091		
R-squared	0.380896	Prob (f-statistic)	0.091
Adjusted R-squared	0.182	AIC	6.87
F-statistic	1.91	Schwarz criterion	7.30
DWS	2.19	Hannan-Quinn	7.02

Source: computed by the author using E-views

Table 4.3 presents the long-term estimates for equations 3.2 to 3.4 in chapter three. The estimated coefficients represent the relationship between fiscal policy and economic growth. A linear function is chosen because Akaike

information criterion (AIC) and Schwarz information criterion (SIC) are the lowest while Durbin Watson (DW) statistic is greater than other models.

The computed R^2 value of 0.38 obtained simply implies that the specified explanatory time series explained about 38% of the total variation in gross domestic product growth rate. The f-statistic of 1.91 which is significant at 10% level indicates that R^2 is insignificant at 5% level and the overall model may not have goodness of fit from the estimated result. The coefficients of tax revenue (TXR), government recurrent expenditure (GRE), and government capital expenditure (GCE) recorded an insignificant impact on economic growth measured by gross domestic product growth rate (GDPg). The signs of the estimated coefficients are contrary to the theoretical expectation. The result discloses that for 1 percentage point increase in tax revenue, GDPg decreases by 0.16 percent. This implies that tax revenue does not positively impact in economic growth in Nigeria.

4.3.1 Test of Hypothesis ($H_0:2$)

From table 4.3 above, the value of t-statistic for tax revenue which is (0.44109) is less than 2. The rule of thumb is that we reject the null hypothesis if the t-statistic is greater than 2. Otherwise, we accept the null hypothesis. In this case, from the estimated model, the t-statistic value is less than 2. Therefore, we do not reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant impact of tax revenue on economic growth in Nigeria. This finding is in line with the works of Peter and Simeon (2011), Agu, Idike and Okwor (2014), Babaloda and Aminu (2014) and Onwe (2014). However, the study contradicted the works of Abdulrauf (2015) and Maku (2015).

4.4.1 Test of Hypothesis ($H_0:3$)

Using table 4.3 above, the value of t-statistic for government recurrent expenditure which is 0.5198 is less than 2. The rule of thumb is that we reject the null hypothesis if the t-statistic is greater than 2. Otherwise, we accept the null hypothesis. In this case, from the estimated model, the t-statistic value is less than 2. Therefore, we do not reject the null hypothesis and concluded that there is no significant impact of government recurrent expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria. This finding contradict the findings of Agu, Idike and Okwor (2014), Osuala and Jones (2014) and Abdulrauf (2015).

4.5.1 Test of Hypothesis ($H_0:4$)

From table 4.3 above, 0.8765 is the value of t-statistic for government capital expenditure which is less than 2. The decision rule is that we reject the null hypothesis if the t-statistic is greater than 2. Otherwise, we accept the null

hypothesis. In this case, from the estimated model the t-statistic value is less than 2. Therefore, we do not reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant impact of tax revenue on economic growth in Nigeria. This finding refutes the work of Chude and Chude (2013) and Onwe (2014).

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

This study was designed to evaluate the impact of fiscal policy on economic growth in Nigeria. In a bid to achieve this objective, ordinary least square (OLS) was used. The result of the unit root test revealed that all variables were integrated of order one at 1% using Augmented Dickey Fuller test. The Granger causality test disclosed a case of no causal relationship between fiscal policy and economic growth in Nigeria. The major findings from the study are outlined as follows:

- I. The estimated granger causality test shows evidence of no causality or independence between fiscal policy and economic growth in Nigeria.
- ii. Tax revenue recorded a negative though statistically insignificant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria. This result throws up several issues that revenue accrued from taxation is either diverted into private coffers or not channeled properly into productive investment which will stimulate economic growth.
- iii. Government recurrent expenditure showed a positive but statistically insignificant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria. This result again questions the heavy amount spent on recurrent items without significant positive impact on economic growth in Nigeria.
- iv. Government capital expenditure disclosed an insignificant negative relationship with economic growth in Nigeria. This result contradicts the experience of great depression in which increase government capital and recurrent spending stimulated economic growth. The result further questions the sincerity of government on amount budgeted for capital expenditure and the kind of project executed.

5.2 Conclusion

This work has attempted to examine the impact of fiscal policy on economic growth in Nigeria. Useful policy options were suggested in line with our findings. Several specifications and empirical literature suggested that fiscal policy would certainly promote economic growth in Nigeria. Overall, the empirical results indicated a case of independence between fiscal policy and

economic growth in Nigeria as well as a negative insignificant effect of tax revenue on economic growth. More so, the empirical result disclosed a case of negative though insignificant effect of government capital expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria.

However, the empirical result revealed that government recurrent expenditure exhibited positive although insignificant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria. The central opinion of this study is that there is no significant impact of fiscal policy on economic growth in Nigeria. Therefore, the extent to which these issues are given due consideration would determine the contribution of fiscal policy to economic growth in Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

Arising from the findings of this study, the following recommendations were proffered:

- i. Our findings support the need for government to always close all tax collection leakages so that money collected from tax payers are remitted in full to the respective tax authorities.
- ii. Our findings also support the need for government to channel tax proceeds to development oriented projects so that both short term and long term gains would be realized.
- iii. Government should cultivate proper monitoring of projects to ensure that projects are executed according to specification and time bound.
- iv. Community leaders whose projects are sited in their areas should enlighten their youths on the long term benefits of such projects so that youths do not make unnecessary demands on the contractors hence increasing project cost.

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